

Preprint

The environmental bill of the top 10% consumers

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Abstract

The top 10% of global consumers are disproportionately responsible for transgressing planetary boundaries, creating damages for which broader society bears the costs. By monetising the climate change, biosphere integrity, biogeochemical cycle, and freshwater-use footprints for these consumers we estimate annual damages owed of \$1.2-\$3.9 trillion, equivalent to \$1.5k-\$5.1k per person (in \$₂₀₁₇), surpassing international climate and biodiversity financing gaps. The top 10% US consumers see a bill of \$21k-\$69k, equal to 7%-22% of their income or 1%-3% of their wealth. Biodiversity loss and climate change comprise the largest damage bill, together totalling 87%-91% of the global total. These costs highlight the mitigation responsibility of the top 10% and illustrate the potential revenue of environmental taxes if the polluter-pays principle is adopted.

Introduction

There are large inequalities in environmental damage inflicted both between and within countries (1–7). The top 10% of consumers are disproportionately responsible for transgressing planetary boundaries, causing one to two thirds of the overshoot of any given boundary (7). These environmental pressures cause drought, heat stress, eutrophication, ecosystem degradation and ultimately human and animal suffering (8, 9). According to both the “common but differentiated responsibilities” and “polluter pays” principles (10, 11), those causing the damages should also pay for solving them. Here, we monetise the environmental harm caused by the top decile of consumers. This not only illustrates the size of their impacts and corresponding responsibility but also provides justification for environmental taxation.

There are conflicting views surrounding the monetising of nature. Proponents argue that it is a tool to raise awareness, that it can improve incentives and generate funds for sustainable practices, and that monetisation is unavoidable since value is already implicit in any decision made, improving transparency (12, 13). Critics highlight that value depends on the method used, that approaches such as willingness to pay mirror the status-quo distribution of income and wealth, and that it is an instrumental rather than intrinsic understanding of nature and ignores the fact that it is a critical resource that is non-substitutable for other resources (14, 15).

Here, we follow the rationale of Costanza et al. (13) that monetisation does not necessarily equal commodification nor provide support for market tradability. Rather, we aim to highlight the differentiated responsibility of society’s top decile and estimate the potential revenue of environmental taxes. This does not mean that taxation or other monetary measures are the only, or even best policy. Levying environmental taxes does not justify or compensate for the damage. However, tax revenue can help pay for the necessary transitions.

We combine top decile consumption-based footprints (7) for the planetary boundaries of: climate change (CO₂), biosphere integrity (Mean Species Abundance (MSA) loss), biogeochemical cycles (nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P)), and freshwater use with environmental costs from the literature. We calculate the environmental bill owed by the top decile consumers globally and of Brazil, China, Egypt, Germany, India, and the USA – the biggest economies in the world and/or of their continent. We use the Environmental Prices Handbook 2024 (16) for prices of CO₂, P, N, and freshwater use. For MSA loss, we convert the handbook’s price for Potentially Disappeared Fraction to MSA loss using a recent study (18). We scale the prices, given for the EU in €₂₀₂₁, to various countries based on GDP per capita, and deflate them to 2017, the year in which footprints are available (7).

Results

We find that the total environmental damage costs per person in the top 10% consumers worldwide is \$1.5k-\$5.1k (in \$₂₀₁₇; see Figure 1A, and the Supplementary Information (SI) for data tables). The cumulative damages of this global top 10% are \$1.2-\$3.9tn (see Figure 1B, and the SI for data tables). There are big differences in the environmental costs of the top 10% between countries. The bill of the top consumers in the USA is consistently the highest, ranging \$21k-\$69k, equal to 7%-22% of their income or 1%-3% of their wealth. This is in contrast with a bill in India of \$160-\$610, equivalent to 0.3%-1.2% of income or 0.1%-0.2% of wealth.

Total costs are mainly driven by biodiversity loss, which constitutes 64-71% of the global bill, depending on the price estimate used (see the SI). Climate change is second largest at 19-26% of the bill, followed by nitrogen with 8-10%. For individual countries, the distribution is similar although the exact proportions vary somewhat (see **Error! Reference source not found.** and the SI).

Discussion

The total environmental damages of the top 10% are considerable. Even the lower USA estimate equals the \$675 billion gap in biodiversity financing needed by 2030 (19) (in \$₂₀₁₇). The lower global estimate surpasses the New Collective Quantified Goal on Climate Finance promised at the COP29 of \$1 trillion per year for “developing countries” by 2035 (20). The central estimate surpasses the biodiversity and climate financing targets combined. In other words, the potential revenue of environmental taxes is high and can be used to finance necessary transitions. We could only include planetary boundaries for which top 10% footprints and prices were available; adding the missing boundaries (novel entities, land-system change, ocean acidification, atmospheric aerosol loading, and stratospheric ozone depletion) would increase the damage bill.

The difference in the bill between countries reflects the inequalities in consumption and emissions. Note that the top 10% consumers in each country are not necessarily in the top 10% globally. More than 60% of the global top 10% are located in the USA and EU while only about 2% are in India (7), as reflected in their respective higher and lower bill. We scaled environmental prices to the different countries based on GDP per capita. As such, prices are higher in countries with a higher GDP.

The main component of the total bill is damage to biosphere integrity. The indicator for this is (terrestrial) Mean Species Abundance (MSA) loss, which is the difference in species abundance of an ecosystem in its current versus its pristine state multiplied by the size of the ecosystem (21). The available footprint is in an aggregate form: global MSA-loss hectares. Prices are more uncertain for this boundary, since biodiversity loss and its valuation are highly context-specific, dependent among others on ecosystem type, state and location (16). Since there is no price for MSA loss in the literature, we convert the Environmental Prices Handbook’s price for Potentially Disappeared Fraction which is based on European ecosystems and valuations. See the SI for a more elaborate discussion of methods and limitations.

Since local conditions are relevant to biodiversity loss, pricing is less straightforward than with carbon taxation and emission trading where the location of emissions is less important. Nevertheless, many pricing mechanisms also exist for biodiversity conservation (25) which can be implemented, adapted to the specific context.

The design of pricing schemes is important to social outcomes such as inequality. Public resistance against carbon taxes mainly comes from concerns for low-income households, so distributional effects are important for policy support (21, 22). Uniform taxation can be regressive if revenues are not recirculated, while higher taxes for luxury consumption rather than basic goods reduce inequality (23). Financing climate investments through a wealth tax on the top 1% would decrease wealth inequality (to them owning a quarter of wealth in 2050) while addressing the unequal burden of climate damages on lower income communities (24).

We show that the environmental damages caused by the consumption of the top 10% are significant. When monetised and taxed, these financial resources could provide the significant funding required for addressing gaps in biodiversity and climate finance.

Figure 1: The environmental bill of the top 10% consumers in 6 countries and globally, in \$₂₀₁₇, a) per capita in the top 10%, b) cumulative for the whole top 10%. Biodiversity and climate financing targets are added as a reference. Note that we have adjusted the prices per country based on GDP per capita. Therefore, each country has their own environmental prices and summing the cumulative top 10% bills does not equal the world total.

Figure 2: Contribution of each planetary boundary bill to the total environmental bill (central estimates) for the world and six countries. See the SI for the lower and upper estimates.

Materials and methods

Tian et al. (7) provide per capita consumption-based carbon (CO₂), phosphorus (P), nitrogen (N), freshwater use, and (terrestrial) biodiversity loss (Mean Species Abundance loss, MSA loss) footprints per expenditure decile (based on household survey data). To monetise the footprints, we use environmental prices from the Environmental Prices Handbook 2024 (16). The handbook has prices for CO₂, N, P, and water consumption, with lower, central, and upper estimates. For biodiversity, the handbook has prices for Potentially Disappeared Fraction (PDF) rather than MSA loss. We convert the PDF prices into MSA loss prices using a recent study that finds a consistent positive relationship between PDF and MSA loss (18). Environmental prices are given in €₂₀₂₁ for EU27, which we convert to \$₂₀₁₇, the year for available footprints (7), and scale to countries/the world based on GDP per capita as recommended in the handbook. We multiply each country's top 10% footprint (7) by the price of the respective substance and sum them to produce the total environmental damage costs per capita and for the whole top 10%. We compare this with the top 10% income and wealth as a reference for environmental taxation. Full methods and all calculations can be found in the SI.

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Author contributions

I.S., R.H., and P.B. designed research; I.S. performed research; I.S., R.H., and P.B. analysed data; and I.S., R.H., and P.B. wrote the paper.

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Supplementary information

Extended methods

All data and calculations can be found in the separate supplementary excel file "Environmental_bill.xlsx". Here we provide more detail on methods. Tian et al. (1) calculate per capita consumption-based carbon (CO₂) phosphorus (P), nitrogen (N), freshwater use, (terrestrial) biodiversity loss (Mean Species Abundance loss, MSA loss) and land-use (Human Appropriation of Net Primary Productivity, HANPP) footprints per expenditure decile (based on household survey data) for 168 countries and the global total based on GTAP¹. We take the footprints for the top 10% globally and several countries as illustrations - Brazil, China, Egypt, Germany, India, and USA as the biggest economies in the world and/or of their continent - to calculate the environmental damage costs.

To monetise the footprints, we use the Environmental Prices Handbook 2024 (2) which provides estimates of prices for various of the planetary boundaries generally using willingness-to-pay valuation methods (see the respective chapters in the handbook). They represent the social damage of environmental pollution per unit of pollutant/water meaning the loss of economic welfare for an additional unit of the pollutant/water released into or extracted from the environment. The handbook has prices for CO₂, N, P, and water consumption, with lower, central, and upper estimates. For biodiversity, the handbook has prices for Potentially Disappeared Fraction (PDF) rather than MSA loss. To our knowledge, there is no direct price for MSA loss in the literature. Therefore, we convert the PDF prices into MSA loss prices using a recent study that finds a consistent positive relationship between PDF and MSA loss (3) (see below). To our knowledge there is no price for HANPP in the literature, so this is not included in our estimates.

We first calculate the environmental costs per planetary boundary. Each planetary boundary (CO₂, N, P, water, MSA loss) has its own worksheet in the accompanying Excel spreadsheet file (sheets 2-6). In each sheet, Table X.1 contains the per capita environmental footprint of the top 10% consumers of the world, Brazil, China, Egypt, Germany, India, and the USA (the biggest economies in the world and/or of their continent) given by Tian et al. (1). These consumption-based footprints are based on household survey data. Note that Tian et al. (1) use survey data to calculate the share of various consumption categories as a proportion of total consumption and then use that to split the macro-economic data on household demand in GTAP, to circumvent the limitation that surveys notoriously underrepresent the top spenders.

We then calculate the environmental costs of that footprint using various environmental prices. Each sheet's Table X.2 contains the lower, central and upper environmental price from the Environmental Prices Handbook (2) in €₂₀₂₁, which we convert to €₂₀₁₇ per country (see the next section). In Table X.3, we then multiply these 2017 prices with the per capita footprint to arrive at the lower, central and upper damage costs for that specific planetary boundary. We take the prices directly from the handbook, except for MSA loss for which we must convert the available price, see the section on MSA loss.

In sheet 7, *Total bill*, we sum the individual environmental per capita costs for total per capita costs. We multiply the per capita bill by 10% of the population as per the World Bank (indicator code SP.POP.TOTL(4)) (table 7.5) for the total bill of the top 10%. We show the results both in euro and dollar, using the average exchange rate in 2017 given in sheet 8. *Currency conversions* (Table 8.3). We also calculate the environmental bill as a proportion of pre-tax income and wealth. For this, we use the top 10% average national income and top 10% average net personal wealth in 2017 from the World Inequality Database (5). This is in 2023 currency, which we convert to 2017 using deflators as described below. Note that the group of global top 10% spenders is not necessarily identical to the top 10% income earners or top 10% wealth owners, so the percentages are not exact but illustrative.

¹ The authors provided us with their calculated footprints (the data displayed in their Supplementary Figures 1-6), for which we are grateful.

Converting prices to \$₂₀₁₇ scaled by country/world

In sheet 8, *Currency conversions*, we list the GDP series used for the calculations. Table 8.1 contains GDP per capita in PPP from the World Bank (indicator code NY.GDP.PCAP.PP.KD (6)) for each country in 2021 (the year of the environmental prices). We calculate the ratio of the respective country's/world's GDP per capita to the EU. In the respective sheet for each planetary boundary, we multiply this ratio with the environmental price, to scale the environmental prices to each country/the world as recommended in the Environmental Prices Handbook for converting EU27 prices to other areas.

Table 8.2 contains a GDP deflator series from the World Bank (indicator code NY.GDP.DEFL.KD.ZG (7)). This provides annual inflation percentages, which we convert using 2017 as a base year from which we calculate specific deflators to 2017 (the year of the footprints). In each planetary boundary sheet, we multiply these with the environmental price, to deflate €₂₀₂₁ to €₂₀₁₇ prices. We also use these deflators to deflate the climate and biodiversity financing targets that we use as reference values for the total environmental bill.

Finally, Table 8.3 has the average exchange rate in 2017 between euro and dollar to convert between the currencies (8).

MSA loss price

Mean Species Abundance (MSA) loss is the difference in species abundance of an ecosystem in its current versus its pristine state multiplied by the size of the ecosystem (9). The available footprint is in an aggregate form: global MSA-loss hectares. The Environmental Prices Handbook (2) does not have prices for MSA loss, but does for another biodiversity indicator, Potentially Disappeared Fraction (PDF). Both are measured on a scale of 0 to 1, where 1 means the area is like its pristine state and 0 that all species have disappeared.

A recent study (3) investigates how MSA loss and PDF are related based on both simulated and empirical data. They find a significant ($p < 0.001$) positive relationship between the two. The relationship is not linear and varies along the value of PDF (0-1). From their supplementary data file (of the version with at least 10 species sampled, $n = 13,968$) we use the central predicted MSA loss value and the lower and upper bound per 0.01 step in PDF value (see sheet 6, Table 6.a). For each point on the curve, we divide the lower, central and upper MSA loss by PDF to determine the ratios between the two (table 6.b). We take the average ratios over the whole curve, excluding the data points at 0-0.05 PDF since the authors indicate the variance in MSA loss is high at such low PDF values. The handbook has prices in €/PDF.m².yr. We convert PDF to MSA loss using the calculated ratios and m² to hectares, to match the MSA loss.ha.yr footprint (Table 6.c). The handbook used a 1% annual price increase in the value of biodiversity to arrive at €₂₀₂₁. Therefore, we use a 1% annual price decrease to get to €₂₀₁₇.

Limitations

Converting PDF to MSA loss prices comes with limitations. The study relating the two finds that PDF explains about half the variance of MSA loss and MSA loss occurs before local extinctions, concluding that the two indicators complementary (3). The relationship between the two shows a slight s-shaped curve, so the ratio between MSA loss and PDF varies along the curve meaning that the level of MSA loss is relevant to the ratio it has with PDF. However, we only have an aggregated MSA loss footprint, so we cannot determine at what level the MSA loss occurs. We use the average ratio of the curve, but use lower, central and upper estimates of MSA loss at each point along the curve, giving a range. The PDF price is based on European ecosystems and land use. Since the handbook indicates valuation depends among others on type, size and species richness of ecosystems, which vary greatly around the world, only using GDP per capita ratios to transfer the prices from EU27 to other regions is a rough estimation and it would be better to establish valuations per region. For a full pricing of biodiversity, the MSA loss footprint also needs to be disaggregated.

The footprints (1) we use only consider consumption and attribute all emissions to consumers (government and gross fixed capital formation emissions are proportionally attributed to households), so assets and ownership are not taken into account. For the top 10% about half of emissions originate

from investments (10), so the footprints and damage costs would increase when taking this into account.

SI references

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